

Origin-destination-based public transport connectivity measures for enhancing service equity

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Summary

An efficient and equitable public transport (PT) network should aim to offer fair connectivity for all urban inhabitants at all times. Building upon the open-sourced data and tools, we have developed a new set of connectivity measures that use the disaggregated origin-destination (OD) level of analysis. The proposed measures focus on the relative competitiveness against driving and the complexity of multiple possible routes. We use hierarchical clustering to group the OD to help visualising the spatial variability of connectivity for Santiago de Chile. The next steps are to create a single combined metric and compare the connectivity temporally.

KEYWORDS: public transport, connectivity, equity, origin-destination, open data

1. Introduction

A sustainable, resource-efficient urban public transport (PT) system needs to be fair for all travellers and be competitive against driving in order to reduce car use. Planners can design the routes and service level to adapt to the demand. However the demand-driven approach to maximise utilisation may neglect to cater for the travel needs for different purposes and on less traversed routes, leading to an unfair distribution of PT resources. The location-based methods such as cumulative opportunities (El-Geneidy and Levinson, 2006) and accessibility index (Wu and Hine, 2003) provide useful methods for comparing the relative accessibility of different origin locations, and combining with socio-demographic data to identify poorly served population groups (Currie et al, 2010). These are often also easier to understand through informative 2-d spatial mapping. However, such approaches cannot distinguish the variations of connectivity *between* different parts of a city easily. Hussain et al (2021) in response developed an origin-destination (OD)-based method using open schedules and route planner tool to generate the routes and observed demand to calculate the vehicle occupancy and available capacity at each origin. However they focus only on the route with minimum travel cost for each OD and ignore the modes and routes information that can offer insight about the range of services available.

The objective of this study is to explore the spatial variations of the PT provision using a series of supply-based features extracted using open data sources and tools. Instead of focusing solely on the fastest route, we interrogate multiple route options and calculate the resilience and coverage features for each OD. This new approach enables researchers and planners to conduct spatially sensitive analyses on PT services more effectively, highlighting gaps in the provision, to improve the network and service design and to increase the competitiveness against car travel.

The analysis demonstrates the differences between the proposed OD features and their variations between ODs. The result can be plotted on directional plots highlight areas with poorer connectivity and clustered to highlight groups with similar feature across a city.

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2. Methodology

We have developed a methodological framework of connectivity measurement that uses open data and tools to ensure the general applicability to any urban PT system. Specifically, we use open-access PT schedules in commonly available General Transit Feed Specification format, open-sourced street layouts from OpenStreetMap, and the open-sourced OpenTripPlanner (OTP) (OpenTripPlanner, 2024) for route planning.

After dividing the city into traffic analysis zones (TAZ), we use OTP to calculate the driving route and the PT routes from the centroid of each origin zone to the centroid of each other destination zones. A resilient PT network may facilitate multiple viable PT route options for each OD, and the PT access points may be located at convenient locations for users for better coverage.

Many of the existing metrics in the literature measures the supply from a zone using measures such as frequency and capacity, see a review in Hussain et al (2021). Hussain and colleagues have explored some OD-based metrics that take into account of available capacity but requires known demand for its calculation. We have selected from some of the existing metrics and expanded them so that they can be derived from open data, harnessing the detail route level data available from route planner tools and analyse them at the OD level.

Therefore, we have derived five connectivity features for each directional OD, listed in Table 1, making use of the speed, distance, travel time, route, route trajectory information from the PT route options returned from OTP.

Table 1 The five OD-based features to measure the PT connectivity

	Purpose of measurement	Calculation
Straightness	Measure whether the route could be constrained by the geography (eg rivers and urban bypasses), or by the planners to cover a larger demand catchment area	Euclidean distance divided by the route distance of the faster PT route
Speed	Indicate the competitiveness against driving speed	Speed of the faster PT route divided by the speed of the driving route
Inconvenience	Incorporate the additional inconvenience of waiting and transferring between services	Unweighted driving time divided by weighted PT travel time PT travel time can be weighted by relative inconvenience. We apply the weight of 2 to the waiting time and add 3.5 minutes for each PT transfer. (Wong and Yap 2023)
Resilience	Indicate whether there are multiple, non-overlapping route options for OD The idea is to find any distinct route options from O to D as a back up in case one of them is not available. The less overlap the two options have, the lower chance that both options will fail and the higher the score.	The minimum of $1 - (\# \text{ overlap zones} / \# \text{ all zones covered by both options})$, for all pairwise route options If the trajectory of option 1 covers zones A, B and C, and option 2 covers B, C and D, then the score will be $1 - (2/4) = 0.5$
Coverage	Measure the zonal area that can reach the service points which have the route options to the destination This feature explicitly works out the coverage of only the useful service points rather than all within the zone	Proportion of the zonal area covered by the 400m walking buffer for each service point that are served by the service route of the first leg of all OD route options

The higher the values of these features, the higher the connectivity for the OD. These values may be normalised within each scenario but it may lose the comparability between times and urban regions. We have not normalised them in our case study below.

We then use hierarchical clustering to group the OD into clusters of similar features and to provide additional explainability. We have also grouped the ODs between sectors for visual interpretation.

We demonstrate this approach by applying to the complex and comprehensive PT network in Santiago de Chile with the schedule data of January 2023. We have calculated the connectivity features between all ODs on a Tuesday at 0800, making it comparable to the general accessibility approach.

3. Results and findings

The government of Santiago de Chile has designated 796 TAZs to cover the Greater Santiago area. The method described above generates 612,646 OD pairs with valid PT routes. **Table 2** describes the distribution of the features for all these ODs.

Table 2 The statistics of each of the connectivity features

	Straightness (p_circ)	Speed (p_speed)	Inconvenience (p_gjt)	Coverage (p_cov)	Resilience (p_resil)
mean	0.6949	0.3957	0.6918	0.7965	0.7778
std	0.1106	0.1154	0.0592	0.2422	0.2299
min	0.1334	0.0490	0.5000	0.0000	0.0000
25 th perc	0.6274	0.3146	0.6550	0.6736	0.7000
Median	0.7052	0.3807	0.6950	0.8936	0.8571
75 th perc	0.7728	0.4577	0.7324	0.9996	0.9355
max	1.0000	1.3210	0.9300	1.0000	1.0000

To illustrate how the features can be used to compare between origin locations, **Figure 1** shows the directional radar charts for two selected origin zones. Zone 55 (top row) has faster PT speed towards the north and south-east of the city, but poorer resilience to the west and south of the city, whilst zone 106 (bottom) has generally higher coverage than zone 55 but the speed compared to cars are worse in most directions.

Figure 1 these directional radar charts show the connectivity feature values for two origin zones (the top is for origin zone 55 in the centre-north of Santiago, and the bottom for zone 106 in the west).

Lighter outer dots represent higher values and darker inner for lower values, the outer grey circle represents the value of 1. The chart is organised by the compass direction of each OD movement, with north pointing at the top of the page.

The ODs are also grouped into five clusters using hierarchical clustering with Ward method using just the five features only. The number of clusters was chosen using silhouette scores and a dendrogram. Figure 2 and the table below show that some clusters are more different than others, and coverage and resilience features are more dissimilar between clusters. The five clusters identified can be summarised as below:

- Cluster 1: High coverage and high resilience
- Cluster 2: Very low resilience with average of only one viable PT option
- Cluster 3: High coverage and low resilience, have the shortest average distance and most route options are bus-only
- Cluster 4: High resilience but mediocre coverage, which means there are multiple route options but they are not easily walkable to catch
- Cluster 5: Low coverage and have the longest average travel distance

It reveals that the route straightness, travel speed and the inconvenience may be indistinguishable between the OD clusters, but the clusters have very diverged coverage and resilience. Travel distance and mode availability can be used to explain some of the differences.

Figure 2 The distribution of the feature values for each cluster and the distribution of the PT mode used for the fastest PT route (m=metro/rail, b=buses, multi=metro+bus, noPT=walking)

Cluster #	Median value					Euclidean distance (metres)
	Straightness (p_circ)	Speed (p_speed)	Inconvenience (p_gjt)	Coverage (p_cov)	Resilience (p_resil)	
1	0.697	0.389	0.693	0.979	0.900	12092
2	0.737	0.335	0.703	0.618	0.000	13154
3	0.742	0.358	0.705	0.959	0.476	11127
4	0.709	0.379	0.694	0.617	0.813	13463
5	0.698	0.375	0.693	0.304	0.808	14972

Table 3 The median value of each feature and the Euclidean distance of the member ODs for each cluster

4. Conclusions and next steps

Equitable OD connectivity facilitates the movements between different parts of a city for different purposes. With this in mind, this study proposes a set of five connectivity measures that can be influenced by PT service planners.

We have demonstrated with the data from a morning peak in Santiago that there is a significant diversity in the connectivity within a city. The radar chart shows that connectivity from a single origin can vary greatly depending on the destinations. This highlights the additional value of the OD-based connectivity over the location-based accessibility approach. The cluster analysis shows that the PT coverage and resilience may be related to the travel distance and modal availability.

This demonstration with Santiago shows some promising results, however there are several issues that need to be considered further. The supply level within each TAZ can be heterogenous that the choice of the zone centroid or the representative point may affect the results. Some of the features will need to be refined, for instance the range of the inconvenience values is rather limited. The straightness and the speed features do not seem to vary significantly between ODs and among the clusters, they may not be very informative to differentiate the ODs across the city. The differences between the OD clustered should also be explored in greater detail. These will be reviewed in the next iteration of the study.

Moreover we will combine these features into a single metric and to consider the temporal variations of the connectivity by time of the day and day of the week which would be very important for an equity analysis considering other trip purposes. Furthermore, we will apply it to different cities to demonstrate the versatility of the metric.

Nevertheless, this open framework enables transport planners and researchers to understand and identify PT connectivity gaps and apply to any cities with the relevant open data. It is supply-based and covers the aspect that are within the planners' control, that would provide additional insights to planners when considering service changes.

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Biographies

Howard Wong is a part-time PhD candidate in Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London, studying equity in public transport provision. He is also a Principal Transport Planner in Transport for London, specialising in travel behaviour and multi-modal connectivity.

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Appendix

The layout and distribution of transit stops in Santiago de Chile. The red dots are the transit stops (bus, metro or rail) and the faint red lines are the transit lines. The grey polygons show the boundary of the traffic analysis zones used and the grey squares are the zone representative points (nearest OSM node to the zone centroid) where the OD connectivity are calculated from. It is visible from this map that some outer zones have very limited PT spatially coverage.

